

NOTES

Condensation of Ethyl *N*-Arylformimidates with Acid Hydrazides

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In this investigation, condensation of ethyl *N*-arylformimidates and acid hydrazides in absolute ethanol has been attempted.

Ethyl *N*-arylformimidates(I) were prepared according to the method of Roberts and Hussein¹ by heating the corresponding aromatic amines with ethyl orthoformate in the presence of small amount of concentrated HCl.

Acid hydrazides² (II) were prepared by refluxing the corresponding carboxylic ester with hydrazine hydrate (100%) for few hours.

Ethyl *N*-arylformimidates were then condensed with acid hydrazides in absolute ethanol to give the corresponding sym-arylformaldanilhydrazines(III) in good yields:

where Ar = C₆H₅-, Cl-C₆H₄-(o), Cl-C₆H₄-(m)

and Ar' = C₆H₅-, C₆H₅-CH₂-, C₆H₅-CH=CH-, O₂N-C₆H₄-(m), O₂N-C₆H₄-(p).

Basically, the mechanism of this condensation reaction is similar to that of ammonolysis of carboxylic esters^{3,4,5} and may be subject to steric⁶ and polar⁷ effects.

Compounds(III) were purified by recrystallization from pyridine-water mixtures since they were found to be insoluble in most organic solvents such as ethyl alcohol, acetone, acetic acid, ether, petroleum ether, benzene, etc. Their structures were confirmed by chemical analysis and by infrared spectra which showed the absorption bands of C=N-group (6.02-6.29 μ), C=O(5.48) and -NH (2.86-3.13 μ). These compounds were found to form coloured complexes with some transition metal ions such as Fe⁺³, Ni⁺² etc. They

1. Roberts and Hussein, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1960, **82**, 1950.

2. Curtius, Franzen, B., 1926, **35**, 3241.

3. Ingold, "Structure and Mechanism in Organic Chemistry", Cornell University Press, Ithaca, 1953.

4. Warder, *Ber.*, 1881, **14**, 1361.

5. Bender, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, **73**, 1626.

6. Miller et al., *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, **70**, 1946; 1949, **71**, 1245; 1950, **72**, 5635; 1953, **75**, 1150.

7. Corvin, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, 732.

are in this respect similar to the acylimidohydrazines reported by Postoviski and Vershchagina.⁸ However, their biological activity has not been checked yet.

EXPERIMENTAL

Melting points are not corrected. Analysis was carried out by Alfred Bernhardt's Laboratories, Ruhr, Germany. I.R. spectra were measured by Perkin Elmer Infracord Model 137B.

sym-Aroylformaldanilhydrazines(III): A solution of ethyl *N*-arylformimidate (0.01 mole) in 4 ml absolute ethanol was placed in a dry, clean, 50 ml conical flask. The flask was shaken for few minutes and left to stand overnight. A few ml of distilled water was then added, whereby crystals of *sym*-aroylformaldanilhydrazine separated out. The product was recrystallized from pyridine-water mixture. Our findings are listed in table I.

TABLE I

sym-Aroylformaldanilhydrazines (III)

Compound		M.P. °C	Yield %	Formula		Analysis			
Ar	Ar'					C	H	N	Cl
1. C ₆ H ₅ -	C ₆ H ₅ -	213	87	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ N ₃ O	Reqd.	70.25	5.43	17.5	—
					Found	69.80	5.89	17.29	—
2. C ₆ H ₅ -	C ₆ H ₅ CH=CH-	214	69	C ₁₆ H ₁₅ N ₃ O	Reqd.	72.45	5.66	15.8	—
					Found	72.32	5.89	16.0	—
3. C ₆ H ₅ -	C ₂ N-C ₆ H ₄ - (p)	195	79	C ₁₄ H ₁₂ N ₄ O ₃	Reqd.	59.15	4.22	9.72	—
					Found	58.80	4.80	20.41	—
4. C ₆ H ₅ -	C ₆ H ₅ -CH ₂ -	215	72	C ₁₅ H ₁₅ N ₃ O	Reqd.	71.11	5.93	16.60	—
					Found	70.83	5.72	17.16	—
5. C ₆ H ₅ -	O ₂ N-C ₆ H ₄ - (m)	204	73	C ₁₄ H ₁₂ N ₄ O ₃	Reqd.	59.15	4.22	19.72	—
					Found	58.69	4.51	20.40	—
6. ClC ₆ H ₄ - (o)	C ₆ H ₅	197	81	C ₁₄ H ₁₂ N ₃ OCl	Reqd.	61.54	4.75	15.35	13.0
					Found	61.23	4.82	15.20	13.21
7. ClC ₆ H ₄ - (o)	C ₆ H ₅ CH=CH-	214	69	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ N ₃ OCl	Reqd.	64.20	4.67	14.02	11.80
					Found	64.30	4.52	13.90	11.60
8. ClC ₆ H ₄ - (o)	C ₆ H ₅ -CH ₂ -	183	74	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ N ₃ Cl	Reqd.	62.71	4.80	14.97	12.30
					Found	62.43	4.71	14.52	12.70
9. ClC ₆ H ₄ - (o)	O ₂ N-C ₆ H ₄ - (p)	210	79	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ N ₄ O ₃ Cl	Reqd.	52.83	3.45	17.58	11.16
					Found	52.79	3.92	17.10	11.53
10. ClC ₆ H ₄ - (o)	O ₂ N-C ₆ H ₄ - (m)	145	76	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ N ₄ O ₃ Cl	Reqd.	52.83	3.45	17.58	11.16
					Found	53.21	3.90	17.16	11.50

⁸ Postoviski and Vershchagina, *Zhur. Obshcher. Chim.*, 1950, 2139.

Compound Ar Ar'	M.P. °C	Yield %	Formula		Analysis			
					C	H	N	Cl
11. ClC ₆ H ₄ -C ₆ H ₅ - (m)	196	78	C ₁₄ H ₁₂ N ₃ OCl	Reqd.	61.54	4.75	15.36	13.0
				Found	61.37	4.78	15.51	12.71
12. ClC ₆ H ₄ -C ₆ H ₅ CH=CH- (m)	216	67	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ N ₃ OCl	Reqd.	64.20	4.67	14.02	11.80
				Found	64.43	4.92	14.14	11.69
13. ClC ₆ H ₄ =C ₆ H ₅ CH ₂ - (m)	182-3	69	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ N ₄ OCl	Reqd.	62.71	4.80	14.97	12.30
				Found	62.95	4.53	14.85	11.93
14. ClC ₆ H ₄ -O ₂ N-C ₆ H ₄ - (m) (p)	209	76	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ N ₄ O ₃ Cl	Reqd.	52.83	3.45	17.58	11.16
				Found	52.91	3.62	17.74	11.07
15. ClC ₆ H ₄ =O ₂ N-C ₆ H ₄ - (m) (m)	200	80	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ N ₄ O ₃ Cl	Reqd.	52.53	4.45	17.58	11.16
				Found	53.01	3.74	18.00	11.02

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